

Velocity of Esterification in Mixed Solvents.

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Previous experiments (Bhide and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, p. 2102) have shown that if an inert solvent like benzene or ligroin is added to a solution of an organic acid in *isoamyl* alcohol with hydrogen chloride as catalyst, the rate of esterification is increased to many times its original value. As a probable explanation of these results it was suggested at the time that the reaction velocity depends more on the ratio of the concentration of the catalyst to the alcohol rather than on the concentration of the catalyst in the whole solution. If benzene is added to a solution of hydrogen chloride in *isoamyl* alcohol it is very likely that the hydrogen chloride molecules associate themselves with the alcohol molecules, as hydrogen chloride is only sparingly soluble in benzene. From calculations based on this hypothesis it was shown qualitatively that the velocity coefficients experimentally found showed a distinct similarity to those thus calculated.

The above hypothesis may be put to test by carrying out three series of experiments as follows.

(1) The catalyst is very soluble in *isoamyl* alcohol but sparingly soluble in the inert solvent.

(2) The catalyst is equally soluble in *isoamyl* alcohol and the inert solvent.

(3) The catalyst is sparingly soluble in *isoamyl* alcohol but very soluble in the inert solvent.

According to this hypothesis, in the first series of experiments the velocity coefficient ought to increase with increasing quantities of the inert solvent. The velocity coefficient-composition curve is hyperbolic. These experiments have already been carried out.

For the second series of experiments acetone was chosen as the inert solvent and phenylacetic acid as the organic acid. Hydrogen chloride is soluble to the same extent in acetone as in *isoamyl* alcohol. The substances were dried as usual. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Acetone per cent.	...	0	20	40	60	80	90
Velocity coefficient $\times 10^4$	...	620	570	527	480	370	280

The velocity coefficients diminish with increasing quantities of acetone. As the acetone concentration increases the active alcohol-catalyst complexes diminish, and hence the fall in the velocity coefficients. It will be seen, however, that this rate does not decrease to the same extent as would be expected from solubility relations. Thus at 80 per cent. acetone concentration the velocity coefficient ought to be one-fourth of its original value, while actually it is only half. The discrepancy may be sought in the complex nature of the equilibria in such homogeneous solutions.

In the third series of experiments picric acid was chosen as the catalyst and benzene as the inert solvent, the organic acid and the temperature of experiment being the same as before. Picric acid is five times as much soluble in benzene as in *iso*amyl alcohol, the rate of esterification was slow. The percentage of ester formed in eight hours was measured. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Benzene per cent.	...	0	20	40	60	80
Ester per cent.	...	21	9	4	1	Nil.

The figures indicate sufficiently well the effect of benzene. At 80 per cent. benzene concentration the alcohol-catalyst complexes were so much diminished that the esterification was practically stopped.

It will be clear from the above experiments that the solubility of the catalyst in the neutral solvent is the predominant factor in determining the rate of reaction. In order to make these results more comprehensive, experiments were made to study the effect of neutral solvents on the decomposition of ethyl diazoacetate. Unfortunately hydrogen chloride does not act as a true catalyst for this reaction in *iso*amyl alcoholic solutions, ethyl chloroacetate being formed as the main product.

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